

ostrails

Open Science Plan-Track-Assess Pathways

D5.1 Strategy and Status Report for Communication, Engagement Exploitation

Deliverable Number	D5.1
Deliverable Title	Strategy and Status Report for Communication, Engagement Exploitation V1
Version n°	1.0
Status	Final
Type	R — Document, report
Dissemination Level	PU
Work Package	WP5
Lead Beneficiary	CLARIN ERIC
Delivery Date	30 September 2024
Author(s)	Francesca Frontini, Thalassia Kontino, Tassos Stavropoulos, Maria Kontopidi, Anca Hienola
Editor(s)	Francesca Frontini & Thalassia Kontino (CLARIN)
Reviewers	Elli Papadopoulou (ARC), Joaquín López Lérida (LIFEWATCH ERIC)
Approved by	Natalia Manola (OpenAIRE)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe framework programme under grant agreement No. 101130187. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the European Research Executive Agency can be held responsible for them.

Revision History

VERSION	STATUS	DATE	DESCRIPTION	AUTHOR(S)
0.0	Draft		Agreement on structure & References	Francesca Frontini, Thalassia Kontino, Tassos Stavropoulos, Maria Kontopidi, Anca Hienola
0.1	Draft		First Draft	Francesca Frontini, Thalassia Kontino, Tassos Stavropoulos, Maria Kontopidi, Anca Hienola
0.2	Review		Intermediate version	Joaquín López Lérida, Elli Papadopoulou
1	Final		Comments Addressed	Tassos Stavropoulos, Francesca Frontini

Author List

ORGANISATION	NAME	CONTACT INFORMATION
CLARIN ERIC	Francesca Frontini	francesca.frontini@ilc.cnr.it
CLARIN ERIC	Thalassia Kontino	t.kontino@uu.nl
CLARIN ERIC	Daan Broeder	d.g.broeder@uu.nl
OpenAIRE	Tassos Stavropoulos	tassos.stavropoulos@openaire.eu
ARC	Maria Kontopidi	m.kontopidi@athenarc.gr
FMI	Anca Hienola	anca.hienola@fmi.fi

Contribution List

ORGANISATION	NAME	CONTACT INFORMATION
OSTrails	All WP5 partners	-ostrails-wp5@openaire.eu

Table of Contents

Disclaimer.....	5
Abbreviations list.....	6
Executive Summary.....	7
1. Introduction	8
1.1. Purpose and scope.....	8
1.2. Methodology.....	8
2. Stakeholders and Future Users	9
2.1. General Target Audience	9
2.2. National and thematic dimensions	12
2.3. Liaison with EOSC and other initiatives.....	15
3. Communication Strategy	16
3.1. Objectives of the Communication Strategy	16
3.2. Project Channels, Tools & Platforms	17
3.2.1. Branding and Visual Identity	17
3.2.2. Website	17
3.2.3. Social Media	18
3.2.4. Newsletter	19
3.2.5. Adoption Stories	19
3.2.6. Webinars.....	20
3.2.7. Zenodo Community.....	20
3.2.8. OSTrails Reporting Form for Events.....	20
3.2.9. Participant Feedback Form	20
3.3. Use of Project Channels, Tools & Platforms across partners	21
3.3.1. Social Media	21
3.3.2. Webinars and Training Sessions	21
3.3.3. Newsletters	21
3.3.4. Dedicated Websites and Portals	22
3.4. Monitoring progress	22
4. Engagement Strategy.....	23
4.1. Objectives of the Engagement Strategy.....	23
4.2. Partner Engagement Channels and Tools	24

4.3. Target Stakeholders in Engagement	25
4.4. Monitoring Progress.....	25
5. Exploitation Strategy	27
5.1. Objectives of the Exploitation Strategy	27
5.2. Key Exploitable Results (KERs).....	27
5.3. Partner Networks in Exploitation.....	28
5.4. Monitoring Progress.....	28
6. Conclusion - Towards an OSTrails Value Proposition	29
7. Annex	31

List of Tables

Table 1. Targeted Stakeholders.....	31
Table 2. OSTrails targeted stakeholders' key messages and channels.....	32
Table 3. Partner's networks.	33
Table 4. Partners Communication, Dissemination & Engagement Activities, Targeted Stakeholders and Tools.....	37
Table 5. Completed Events.	43
Table 6. Communication, Dissemination and Engagement KPIs.....	48
Table 7. Exploitation KPIs.....	52
Table 8. OSTrails website views per article.....	53

List of Figures

Figure 1. European Coverage and Budget Division of OSTrails.....	13
Figure . Sitemap of OSTrails website	18

Disclaimer

This document contains description of the OSTrails project findings, work, and products. Certain parts of it might be under partner Intellectual Property Right (IPR) rules so, prior to using its content please contact the consortium head for approval.

In case you believe that this document harms in any way IPR held by you as a person or as a representative of an entity, please do notify us immediately.

The authors of this document have taken any available measure to ensure that its content is accurate, consistent, and lawful. However, neither the project consortium as a whole nor the individual partners that implicitly or explicitly participated in the creation and publication of this document hold any sort of responsibility that might occur as a result of using its content.

The publication herein was produced in the framework of the EU-funded OSTrails project (Grant Agreement No 101130187). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the OSTrails consortium and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency.

**Funded by
the European Union**

Abbreviations list

IVOA International Virtual Observatory Alliance

IPDA International Planetary Data Alliance

IHDEA International Heliophysics Data Environment Alliance

KPI Key performance Indicators

maDAP Machine actionable Data Management Plans

RDA Research Data Alliance

PSC Project Steering Committee

SKG Scientific Knowledge Graph

Executive Summary

This deliverable presents the strategy that the OSTrails partners will implement for Communication, Engagement as well as Exploitation of the project's outcomes to the relevant communities and stakeholders.

The report was prepared within the scope of Work Package 5 and covers the main relevant aspects, including the list of relevant stakeholders and future users that will be the target of specific activities and the communication strategy as well as channels and tools. It also contains indications of the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) that will be used to monitor the activities.

Moreover, the document also outlines the roadmap for an OSTrails value proposition, that will be tailored for the needs of both EOSC and national users.

1. Introduction

1.1. Purpose and scope

The purpose of the present deliverable is to define the **strategy** and foreseen activities in terms of communication and outreach for the OSTrails project. The scope is to:

- Identify target communities and overall objectives.
- Outline the plan for the overall Communication, Engagement, Exploitation strategy, set the goals and identify initiatives to be carried out.
- Outline the OSTrails Value proposition to highlight the benefits of the project's results to the broader community of stakeholders.

D5.1 is developed within the framework of WP5, collecting input from tasks related to Communication & Dissemination (T5.1), User Engagement (T5.3) and Liaison with other projects and EOSC (T5.4). This is the first of two deliverables of its kind and an updated version "*Status Report for Communication, Engagement Exploitation V2*" is expected at the end of the project.

The OSTrails strategy for Communication, Engagement and Exploitation aims at:

- Identifying the appropriate means and channels to disseminate OSTrails' activities and results (**Communication Plan**).
- Achieving a large level of active user engagement from national and research communities (**User Engagement Activities**).
- Clearly communicating the project's added value to other EOSC implementers and relevant bodies (**Value proposition**).

To achieve this, close contact with the technical work packages (WP1, 2, 3) must be ensured, to find appropriate ways to bring the results to the relevant stakeholders. Moreover, individual pilots' partners (WP4) will have to harmonize their communication and engagement strategy with the overall project's objectives.

Lastly, in view of conceiving a well-adjusted plan, the various project partners represented in WP5 have been asked to provide their input on the various aspects touched upon in this document, and to outline their planned activities (see

Table 4).

1.2. Methodology

The strategy outlined in this deliverable is based on stakeholder input gathered through structured consultations with project partners. Contributions were provided via collaborative spreadsheets created and stored in the project's shared folder on Teams,

also available in the **Annex**. These inputs were systematically integrated to ensure the communication plan aligns with the requirements of the technical work packages and of the 24 pilots¹ that will implement the project results in their own settings.

The use of shared spreadsheets facilitated:

- **Efficient data collection:** Each partner could input their planned activities, stakeholder engagements, and dissemination efforts in a structured format.
- **Collaboration across teams:** Centralized storage in Teams allowed all project partners to review, update, and contribute to the plan in real-time.
- **Harmonization of strategies:** This approach ensured that communication and engagement strategies at the national level were aligned with the overall project objectives and that partner-specific needs were addressed in a coordinated way.

This process guarantees that the deliverable reflects the collective input and feedback from all relevant stakeholders and partners across the project.

2. Stakeholders and Future Users

2.1. General Target Audience

The OSTrails project is designed to engage a diverse set of stakeholders across the research and open science ecosystems (see below, **Engagement Strategy**). This section outlines the general target audience, originally identified in the **Grant Agreement** (GA) and further refined by the input provided by project partners (**Table 1**Table 2 and

Table 4). These target groups are central to guiding the project's communication, engagement, and exploitation strategies, ensuring the adoption and sustainability of OSTrails' tools and methodologies.

Below, we list the different types of stakeholders that we identified, providing descriptions and specifying their needs according to the Plan-Track-Assess Framework (Reichmann et al., 2024) that OSTrails develops, and the role they undertake in the research ecosystem.

1. Researchers

- **Description:** Researchers from various disciplines are at the core of the OSTrails project. This group includes individual researchers, research groups, and academic institutions that produce, manage, and publish data.
- **Needs:** Researchers require tools to improve the management and FAIRness (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) of their data and research outputs. They also need resources to comply with open science mandates, which OSTrails

¹ See also: D4.1 Pilots Methodology and Operational Processes. <https://ostrails.eu/deliverables>

addresses through solutions like the **Scientific Knowledge Graph (SKG)** and **machine-actionable Data Management Plans (maDMPs)**.

- **Role:** End-users of the tools developed in OSTrails, key participants in pilots, and contributors to (meta)data quality improvements.

2. Data Stewards and Librarians

- **Description:** Data stewards and librarians support researchers in managing research data and ensuring they adhere to FAIR principles and Research Data Management (RDM) best practices. They help researchers with publishing their outputs in open access and ensure proper data stewardship.
- **Needs:** This group requires **training and tools** to implement FAIR guidance in their local environments as well as to support the adoption of maDMPs and improve data curation.
- **Role:** Facilitators who bridge the gap between researchers and infrastructure developers by ensuring data is managed correctly, is discoverable and can be reused.

3. Infrastructure Developers

- **Description:** Infrastructure developers are responsible for building and maintaining systems that support RDM and ensure interoperability across platforms. These stakeholders are crucial in integrating OSTrails tools within the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) and other research infrastructures (see below, National and thematic dimensions).
- **Needs:** This group requires technical specifications, common models, and APIs, such as the **OSTrails Interoperability Reference Architecture**, to improve data infrastructure and connect repositories and PTA services across research communities.
- **Role:** Providers of the technical backbone that allows research data to be seamlessly exchanged across platforms.

4. Repository Managers and Publishers

- **Description:** Repository managers and academic publishers are tasked with ensuring that research outputs are stored, curated, and disseminated effectively. This group manages the platforms where data is deposited and ensures it is accessible to the research community.
- **Needs:** Repository managers need **FAIR assessment tools** and policies to implement in their workflows, while publishers need support for integrating these principles into their submission and publication processes.

- **Role:** Gatekeepers of research outputs who ensure that data remains open, accessible, and reusable for future research.

5. Policy Makers and Funders

- **Description:** Policy makers and research funders shape the strategic direction of research funding, compliance, and governance. Their role is pivotal in driving the adoption of open science practices and ensuring that research data is managed according to FAIR principles.
- **Needs:** They need tools like **maDMPs** to ensure transparency and compliance in research projects, and insights from **FAIR assessments** to track how well funded projects align with open science mandates.
- **Role:** Influencers who set the frameworks and requirements for how research data should be managed and shared, ensuring sustainability and compliance within the scientific community.

6. EOSC and Open Science Communities

- **Description:** This group includes members of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) and related open science communities, such as EOSC-related working groups, task forces, and science clusters. They are central to the adoption and integration of OSTrails outputs within the broader research ecosystem.
- **Needs:** These communities require tools and services including documentation, guidelines and training resources that can be integrated into the EOSC framework, promoting data sharing and interoperability across Europe.
- **Role:** Champions of open science who will promote the adoption of OSTrails tools across research infrastructures and ensure they are aligned with European open science goals.

This diverse target audience reflects the broad impact and utility of the OSTrails project. By tailoring our communication, engagement, and exploitation strategies to the needs and roles of these key groups, as identified in the Grant Agreement and updated through partners input, OSTrails will foster greater adoption of its tools and ensure long-term sustainability within the open science landscape, ultimately contributing to the development of the EOSC.

User engagement and communication activities will thus be aimed at raising awareness about the results of the project to the relevant target group, to stimulate the uptake of the proposed solutions and developed tools.

We list here the main target stakeholder groups of such activities (see also Table 1):

- **Researchers and data stewards**

- *Expected outcome:* Improvement in the way research outputs are shared and reused within and across research disciplines, enhancing the quality, validation and productivity of research.
- **Repository managers, infrastructure developers, research managers/executives**
 - *Expected outcome:* Better access to and increasing volumes of research data following FAIR principles (that are open as possible) and other research outputs stimulating the development and uptake of a wide range of new innovative and value-added services from public and commercial providers, as well as facilitate scientific cooperation.
- **Funders, research executives, policy makers**
 - *Expected outcome:* Increased trust in science through increased FAIRness, openness and quality of scientific research in Europe, supported by more meaningful monitoring and better facilitators for reproducibility, validation, reuse of research results, by improving pathways for science communication for public.

Engagement and dissemination activities must be adapted to the various types of target groups, as will be shown in paragraphs [Communication Strategy](#) and [Engagement Strategy](#)).

2.2. National and thematic dimensions

OSTrails is a multistakeholder consortium of technical experts, research infrastructures representatives, communities of researchers and research support staff from different countries and disciplines as well as research funders, all working together to co-design, test and adopt the OSTrails methods and tools, each in their own setting. These key national and disciplinary stakeholders will be involved in different ways in user engagement activities within WP5.

Among them, an important subgroup is constituted by research data infrastructures that are or aim to be part of the EOSC, and that can further be distinguished along the axis of European (or international) vs national dimension, as well as the generalist vs disciplinary dimension.

At the **national level**, we build on the services, policies and collaborations of consortium partners bringing together key national actors, initiatives and infrastructures, incl EOSC mandated organizations, aiming to improve existing infrastructure with OSTrails standards and connect it with the EOSC. This dimension is most prominent within the activities of the national pilots (WP4) (see also [Figure 1](#)). These pilots' implementation plans detailed in [D4.1 Pilots Methodology and Operational Processes](#), involve the

organisation of events both to co-create results and to bring awareness to local communities regarding OSTrails advancements and their use in each country.

Figure 1. European Coverage of OSTrails.

To further improve dissemination of the OSTrails' outcomes, user engagement events will be extended to all mandated organizations within the EOSC, as well as the future national EOSC nodes.

At the **European level**, the main stakeholder is the EOSC, including the association, working groups such as [task forces](#) and [opportunity areas](#), and other projects (see below, Par. 2.3). Within the EOSC disciplinary nodes, the **science clusters** play an important role in reaching out to all disciplinary infrastructures. All five [Science Clusters](#) are represented in OSTrails by one or more infrastructures and pilots. These partners will disseminate the project's results within their communities but also extend with dedicated events to other disciplinary infrastructures within their cluster as well as to national disciplinary nodes.

Since most EOSC infrastructures belong to **ESFRI**, the latter will also be an important stakeholder, and the [EOSC-ESFRI coordination task force](#) can be an important channel to facilitate communication and exchange of information. Similarly, since many national pilot organisations and / or services are part of the **OpenAIRE** network, the rest of the **NOADs** network will be contacted to seek adoption of OSTrails results in countries that are currently not represented in the consortium.

Finally, the project's outcomes should be disseminated also to **international stakeholders** beyond Europe. This is achieved via some of our partners active involvement in relevant RDA groups and task forces, particularly those dedicated to DMPs and Knowledge Graphs models, incl. the FAIRsharing one. WP5 will ensure an effective communication of engagement and dissemination events also via these channels.

OSTrails partners leverage their established networks, including **EOSC Task Forces**, **working groups**, and other relevant open science communities, to enhance the project's communication and engagement efforts and reach specialized audiences - a detailed description of networks and stakeholders covered by each partner can be found in **Table 3** and **Table 4**. These networks play a vital role in facilitating targeted communication and engagement within professional circles, ensuring that OSTrails tools and developments are disseminated to key stakeholders who are directly involved in research data management, open science policies, and infrastructure development.

1. EOSC Task Forces and Working Groups

- Many partners are actively involved in various [EOSC Task Forces](#) and [Opportunity Areas](#) that focus on key aspects of data management, interoperability, and FAIR principles. By tapping into these networks, partners are able to communicate project updates, technical progress, and new tools directly to the leaders and contributors of the EOSC ecosystem.
- These specialized forums allow OSTrails to reach technical experts and decision-makers who are instrumental in integrating project outcomes into broader European infrastructures.

2. National Open Science Initiatives and NOADs

- Partners also use their affiliations with **national open science initiatives** and **OpenAIRE NOADs** to communicate the project's outputs to local research communities. These national networks provide a platform for targeted dissemination to researchers, data stewards, and infrastructure developers who are focused on implementing open science practices within their countries.
- By engaging with national stakeholders through these networks, partners ensure that the tools and methodologies developed by OSTrails are aligned with national open science strategies and policies.

3. Discipline-Specific Research Infrastructures

- Some partners are connected to **discipline-specific research infrastructures** such as [CESSDA](#), [CLARIN](#), and [DARIAH](#), which cater to particular scientific communities. These networks provide a focused channel for communicating the benefits of OSTrails tools to researchers and data managers working in specific fields, ensuring relevance and adoption within specific domains.

- By using these infrastructures, partners can effectively communicate technical advancements and demonstrate how OSTrails tools can address domain-specific data management challenges.

4. Open Science Advocacy Groups

- Partners involved in open science advocacy groups like [RDA](#) and [LIBER](#) use these platforms to engage with a broad audience of open science supporters. These groups play a key role in promoting OSTrails tools and outputs as part of the broader movement towards open access and FAIR data practices.
- The communication within these networks helps raise awareness of OSTrails developments and encourages the adoption of its tools across different regions and research disciplines.

By leveraging their networks within EOSC, national open science initiatives, discipline-specific research infrastructures, and open science advocacy groups, OSTrails partners ensure that communication efforts are highly targeted and impactful. These specialized networks allow the project to reach the right audiences within technical, policy, and research circles, promoting the adoption and integration of its tools in a strategic and focused manner.

In planning the roadmap of user dissemination and engagement events it is important that the national and thematic dimension are equally targeted, since these stakeholders may have different needs and priorities that must be addressed and underlined. The project's value proposition (see below, Conclusion - Towards an OSTrails Value) will be adapted according to these dimensions.

2.3. Liaison with EOSC and other initiatives

As anticipated above, a core objective of OSTrails' Liaison office is to foster strategic engagement with the European Open Science Cloud and other key initiatives, ensuring alignment with global standards for open science, FAIR data management, and enhanced interoperability of services. OSTrails will liaise with the EOSC Association, science clusters, and a range of complementary projects and initiatives such as the Research Data Alliance (RDA), [CODATA](#), [GO FAIR](#), and EOSC related projects (such as the [OSCARS](#) project). This network of collaborations positions OSTrails at the centre of efforts to build a more integrated, interoperable research data ecosystem.

EOSC exists in a state of persistent flux, with its structure, policies, and service offerings shifting. This instability creates uncertainty for stakeholders, making it difficult to plan long-term strategies and fully commit to its framework. In this context, OSTrails will engage with stakeholders and show how it can provide stability through the solidity of its consortium, maintaining adaptable, robust tools that help users and providers navigate these changes and extract value.

OSTrails works closely with the EOSC Association, particularly through participation in Task Forces and Opportunity Areas. These groups focus on priority areas such as research data interoperability, metadata standards, and resource federation, all of which are critical for the long-term success of EOSC. Participants in OSTrails even lead the efforts of specific EOSC Task Forces and Opportunity Areas, actively contributing to shaping the future of EOSC. OSTrails builds on this momentum, ensuring that its products align with the latest developments while providing the consistency needed to foster widespread adoption.

OSTrails also engages with the science clusters, which bring together scientific communities to address cross-disciplinary challenges and foster collaboration, particularly through collaboration with the OSCARS project.

OSTrails' collaboration with the Research Data Alliance (RDA) is strengthened by the fact that many of its participants are already actively involved in various RDA working groups and initiatives, even co-chairing them. These OSTrails members contribute to international discussions on data sharing, interoperability, and governance, ensuring that the tools and solutions developed within the project are applicable in different regions supporting standardisation of practices and their uptake at global scale.

3. Communication Strategy

3.1. Objectives of the Communication Strategy

Effective communication and dissemination are crucial to the success of OSTrails, as they ensure that our objectives, progress, and results reach and resonate with our stakeholders. This chapter outlines our accomplished, ongoing and planned activities to achieve these goals. As detailed in the roadmap² (which is continuously updated), our approach includes the development of OSTrails' digital identity through a dedicated website, social media channels, and branded materials, as well as the publication of stories and interviews to highlight pilot project achievements.

Our efforts will focus on promoting key results and publications, coordinating scientific publishing, and managing event visibility. Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) have been established to measure the success of these activities, including website traffic, social media engagement, and subscriber growth. The KPI **Table 6** presents clear metrics to evaluate the effectiveness of the project's outreach and engagement activities across all

² [M4 - Interim Products Establishment for Cross-Task Collaboration](#)

partners. A summary of the Communication KPIs, including those achieved, is provided at the end of the chapter.

3.2. Project Channels, Tools & Platforms

3.2.1. Branding and Visual Identity

The OSTrails project has developed a cohesive branding and visual identity to ensure consistent and professional communication across all platforms. A detailed brand guidelines document (PDF) has been created, outlining the use of logos, fonts, colours, and other visual elements. Using these guidelines, we have produced various branded templates, including a presentation template, deliverables template, PSC agenda template, WP rolling minutes template, pilot interview template, and a reporting form template. Additionally, a poster has been designed, all of which are shared in editable formats for easy use by partners. A selection of some of these assets that useful for partners' dissemination activities are also available in our [Press Kit](#).

3.2.2. Website

The OSTrails website (<https://ostrails.eu/>) serves as the primary communication and dissemination platform for the project. It acts as a central hub for project updates, providing continuous and transparent information on all projects' activities. Key features include detailed insights into the project's goals, methodology, consortium partners, services, pilot interviews, news, and upcoming events (**Figure 2**). The site also features a dedicated training corner, designed to host resources that support the adoption and implementation of project outcomes. These elements ensure that users stay informed and engaged throughout the project's progress.

Figure 2. Sitemap of OSTrails website.

3.2.3. Social Media

The OSTrails project is active on Twitter, LinkedIn, and YouTube, offering various gateways for the audience to engage with partners, content, and updates. Social media will be an essential communication tool throughout the project to reach out a broad audience and increase awareness of OSTrails' progress and outcomes. To achieve the best impact and build a stable, engaged audience, OSTrails will also leverage its partners' networks to amplify outgoing messages and maximize the project's visibility. Regular and continuous updates on social media will ensure engagement with the project's key stakeholders. The specific aims of each platform are outlined below:

Twitter (@OSTrails): The Twitter account will focus on maximizing the project's visibility by providing frequent, short updates on OSTrails' actions and activities. The channel will offer weekly or bi-weekly posts, especially in the early stages of the project, highlighting project news, ongoing work, and important milestones. In addition to text-based updates, the Twitter feed will feature short videos, including interviews with partners, promotional videos, and event highlights. Project partners and related institutions will be tagged to help spread the message, while hashtags such as #OpenScience, #ScienceKnowledgeGraph, #FAIRData, #OSTrails, and #EOSC will be used to engage a wider audience. As the project advances and outcomes are finalized, the volume of

Twitter activity will increase, positioning OSTrails at the forefront of key discussions on research innovation.

LinkedIn ([@OSTrails](#)): LinkedIn will be used to engage a more professional audience, focusing on detailed posts that highlight OSTrails' key developments and policy implications. Through frequent updates, OSTrails will share insights, technical achievements, and reports aimed at policymakers, industry professionals, and the research community. The posts will also promote OSTrails' major milestones and progress, as well as collaboration opportunities, using professional language tailored to LinkedIn's audience. Additionally, through leveraging the OpenAIRE LinkedIn account, OSTrails will gain access to an established network, expanding its reach and impact across a broader professional community.

YouTube ([OSTrails - YouTube](#)): YouTube serve as the central hub for video content, offering a dynamic way to showcase OSTrails' progress and outcomes. Starting with an introductory video about the project in the first year, the YouTube channel will grow with the addition of event recordings, instructional videos, and interviews with partners. The aim is to make complex project outcomes more accessible, with a goal of engaging a diverse audience interested in the themes of open science.

3.2.4. Newsletter

The OSTrails project releases a **monthly newsletter**, providing subscribers with key updates, project milestones, and upcoming events. This newsletter is a vital tool for engaging researchers, policymakers, and stakeholders, offering in-depth insights into OSTrails' progress. Each edition focuses on major developments, including updates on the latest technical developments of the OSTrails project., pilot implementations, and partner activities. The newsletter will also feature multimedia content, such as links to YouTube videos, showcasing tutorials, interviews, and event highlights. A dedicated section will promote upcoming events like webinars and training sessions, inviting readers to participate. The newsletter will serve as a consistent source of valuable information, keeping the OSTrails community informed and engaged while complementing the project's social media efforts.

3.2.5. Adoption Stories

Pilot interviews and adoption stories (see, [News - OSTrails](#)) play a key role in sharing the journey of each OSTrails pilot. These stories capture key aspects such as the goals and objectives, challenges faced, and the collaborative tools and procedures used to overcome them. By featuring interviews from both national and thematic pilots, OSTrails encourages adoption and conversation among a wider range of communities. These narratives are shared through OSTrails' newsletters, website, and social media channels to attract stakeholders with similar needs and interests, ultimately promoting OSTrails' methods and tools.

3.2.6. Webinars

Webinars will play a key role in disseminating knowledge and fostering dialogue with the OSTrails community, offering a platform to demonstrate the project's tools, services, and technical developments. These sessions are designed to actively engage researchers, data stewards, and infrastructure developers, providing hands-on guidance and fostering co-creation efforts. Starting in the later stages of the project (from Y2), the webinars will address specific aspects of the SKGs, FAIR assessments, and (ma)DMPs, ensuring participants gain practical insights. In parallel, a **Series of Information Sessions** have been scheduled, with the first taking place in October 2024, aiming at updating the consortium members on key technical developments and innovations within OSTrails. These webinars and sessions will help bridge the gap between theory and application, ensuring widespread adoption of the project's results.

3.2.7. Zenodo Community

A dedicated Zenodo collection ([OSTrails \(zenodo.org\)](https://zenodo.org)) has been created to preserve all outputs of the OSTrails project. Each output will be assigned a DOI (Digital Object Identifier) to ensure long-term accessibility and proper citation. This platform will serve as a permanent repository for deliverables, reports, technical documentation, and other project-related resources, ensuring open access to the wider research community.

3.2.8. OSTrails Reporting Form for Events

To effectively track and monitor the impact of events organized or attended by OSTrails partners, a **reporting form** has been developed. This form collects essential data on the events where OSTrails was presented or discussed, helping to ensure continuous assessment and improvement of engagement strategies. The form is accessible via [this link](#) and is intended to be filled out by any partner involved in an OSTrails-related event. The data gathered will be used for reporting purposes, as well as to inform future engagement and dissemination strategies.

3.2.9. Participant Feedback Form

To collect and analyse participant feedback from events, including webinars, a standardized feedback form is under development. This form will be tailored for different types of OSTrails events (e.g., training, outreach, pilot-related events), ensuring consistent and actionable insights. The feedback will be anonymous, covering key aspects such as content relevance, session organization, and participant satisfaction. The template can

be personalized for each event, while keeping core questions uniform to allow comparative analysis.

3.3. Use of Project Channels, Tools & Platforms across partners

Each OSTrails partner contributes to the communication and dissemination strategy through a variety of platforms and tools, reflecting the unique needs of their respective audiences. Below is a comprehensive discussion of the key patterns observed across the partners' communication channels and platforms.

3.3.1. Social Media

Twitter and **LinkedIn** are the most commonly used social media platforms among OSTrails partners. These platforms are leveraged for frequent updates, announcements, and engagement with the broader research and academic community.

More than 10 partners have reported using Twitter, including OpenAIRE, RBI, Ubelgrade, UPM, ARC, CTU, UNIVIE, CLARIN, ESRF, SOCIB, PSNC, and SURF. LinkedIn is utilized by at least 5 partners, such as OpenAIRE, RBI, ARC, CLARIN, and UNIVIE, to target professional audiences.

3.3.2. Webinars and Training Sessions

Webinars and training sessions are vital for engaging stakeholders and demonstrating OSTrails tools. These sessions create opportunities for live interaction and practical demonstrations, particularly around technical developments.

At least 8 partners have scheduled webinars or workshops, including OpenAIRE, RBI, CTU, UPM, ARC, UNIVIE, CLARIN, and ESRF.

3.3.3. Newsletters

Newsletters are used by several partners to maintain regular contact with stakeholders, providing structured updates on the project's progress and upcoming activities.

At least 5 partners, including OpenAIRE, RBI, Ubelgrade, UMinho, and PSNC, use newsletters to keep their communities informed.

3.3.4. Dedicated Websites and Portals

Partners use dedicated websites and institutional portals to host deliverables, updates, and other project materials. These websites act as centralized hubs for disseminating information to a wide audience.

At least 6 partners, including Ubelgrade, FECYT, OpenAIRE, PSNC, UMinho, and ARC, use dedicated websites or national portals for project dissemination.

OSTrails partners utilize a variety of communication channels and platforms, with social media, newsletters, webinars, and dedicated websites playing critical roles. This diverse strategy ensures comprehensive dissemination and engagement across different research communities and stakeholder groups.

3.4. Monitoring progress

The following KPIs monitor the progress of OSTrails' communication efforts (see [Table 6](#) for Communication KPI details):

- **Branding:** Seven templates have been created and implemented across all outputs: Presentation, Deliverables, Project Steering Committee Agenda, WP Rolling Minutes, Pilot Interviews, Reporting Form, Poster.
- **Website:** The data on OSTrails website views (see [Table 8](#)) shows strong user engagement, particularly with national pilot interviews and key project updates, offering valuable insights to refine the communication strategy and enhance dissemination efforts.
 - **National Pilot Interviews:** The Netherlands (915 views), Czech Republic (581), and Croatia (531) have so far received the most attention, indicating high interest in country-specific project activities.
 - **Key Project Updates:** Major milestones, such as interoperability advancements and international events, garnered significant interest, demonstrating stakeholders' focus on project outcomes.
 - **Educational Resources:** The glossary (619 views) and training sections (1,517 views) are highly valued, reflecting the importance of providing accessible educational content on the planning, tracking and assessing pillars of OSTrails workplan.
 - **Press and Tools:** The press kit so far had 372 views, while the tools section had 135 views, suggesting the need for increased promotion of available resources.

By focusing on popular content and improving the visibility of underutilized resources, OSTrails can further strengthen its communication and dissemination strategy.

- **Social media:** Twitter and LinkedIn have 240 followers and 42 total posts.
- **YouTube:** views will be tracked after content release.
- **Newsletter:** Four newsletters have been published, reaching 192 subscribers so far.
- **Adoption Stories:** Nine stories have been shared, with a target of 24 by project completion, updated two-three times each.
- **Video:** The project video is currently in development and will be released within Year 1.
- **Webinars:** Scheduled to start later in the project, targeting 300 participants.

These KPIs will be updated regularly to measure the effectiveness of the communication strategy.

4. Engagement Strategy

4.1. Objectives of the Engagement Strategy

The primary goal of the OSTrails Engagement Strategy is to foster active collaboration, co-creation, and participation among stakeholders, ensuring that the tools and methodologies developed by the project are understood, adopted, and adapted by relevant communities. By engaging researchers, infrastructure developers, data stewards, and policy makers, the strategy aims to create a sustainable ecosystem around OSTrails' outputs. The specific objectives of the engagement strategy are as follows:

1. Encourage Active Participation in Tool Development

- **Objective:** Involve key stakeholders, such as researchers and infrastructure developers, in the design and testing of OSTrails. This ensures that the tools meet user needs and are aligned with real-world use cases.
- **Method:** Facilitate this through **workshops**, **webinars** where stakeholders provide feedback and co-create solutions tailored to their specific research environments.

2. Promote Adoption and Use of OSTrails Tools

- **Objective:** Ensure widespread adoption of OSTrails outputs by engaging with research communities, data stewards, and institutional repositories to integrate these tools into their workflows.
- **Method:** Conduct **training sessions**, such as **hackathons**, to provide hands-on experience with the tools, empowering stakeholders to incorporate them into their daily practices.

3. Strengthen Collaboration with Research Infrastructures

- **Objective:** Engage with EOSC Task Forces, national research infrastructures, and discipline-specific infrastructures (e.g., CESSDA, CLARIN, DARIAH) to integrate OSTrails tools into existing European and national-level infrastructures.
- **Method:** Leverage partner networks and collaborative working groups to facilitate the seamless integration of OSTrails outputs into broader research infrastructures, thereby increasing their reach and impact.

4. Facilitate Knowledge Sharing and Best Practices

- **Objective:** Encourage knowledge sharing and the dissemination of best practices among stakeholders, particularly regarding FAIR data principles and open science mandates.
- **Method:** Host engagement events, such as **webinars** and **workshops**, where participants can share their experiences, learn from others, and exchange knowledge on how to implement OSTrails tools effectively within their own organizations.

5. Drive Sustainability and Long-Term Engagement

- **Objective:** Ensure that the engagement with stakeholders extends beyond the project's duration, fostering long-term relationships and adoption of OSTrails tools in the broader research ecosystem.
- **Method:** Collaborate with policy makers and funders to embed OSTrails outputs into national and European research strategies and develop partnerships to ensure continued use and development of the tools.

The Engagement Strategy is designed to facilitate collaboration, adoption, and sustainability of OSTrails tools by engaging with a wide range of stakeholders. Through active participation, knowledge sharing, and integration into existing infrastructures, OSTrails aims to create lasting impacts within the open science and research data management communities.

4.2. Partner Engagement Channels and Tools

OSTrails partners engage stakeholders through a variety of hands-on activities designed to encourage collaboration, co-creation, and adoption of project outcomes. These engagement activities include:

- **Workshops and Webinars:** Hands-on training and practical sessions to familiarize stakeholders, including researchers, data stewards, and infrastructure developers, with OSTrails tools such as machine-actionable DMPs (maDMPs), FAIR assessment services, and the Scientific Knowledge Graph (SKG). These sessions enable stakeholders to provide feedback and directly shape the tools they use.

- **Training Sessions:** Specific educational programs, both online and face-to-face, aimed at building capacity within research communities and helping users integrate OSTrails tools into their daily workflows. These events target key groups like research support staff, repository managers, and data stewards.
- **Hackathons and Co-Creation Events:** Collaborative coding and problem-solving events where developers, researchers, and technical experts work together to develop and improve OSTrails functionalities. These activities are critical for fostering innovation and real-time tool testing.
- **Engagement through Networks:** Partners leverage their participation in national and international networks—such as EOSC Task Forces, the Research Data Alliance (RDA), and national Open Science initiatives—to foster strategic collaborations. These networks play a crucial role in integrating OSTrails outputs into existing infrastructures and aligning them with global standards.

For detailed partner-specific channels and platforms, refer to **3.3.5 Partner Networks in Communication** and **3.3.1 Webinars and Training Sessions**.

4.3. Target Stakeholders in Engagement

The key groups involved in OSTrails' engagement efforts include stakeholders who actively participate in co-creation, adoption, and integration of the project's tools and services. For the general as well as the partner-specific target audience, refer to **Stakeholders and Future Users**.

4.4. Monitoring Progress

The engagement strategy of OSTrails is designed to track the effectiveness of stakeholder participation and the overall outreach of project results. The following Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) measure the success of these efforts, ensuring OSTrails effectively engages relevant communities, promotes adoption of its tools, and fosters collaboration milestones (see **Table 5** and **Table 6** for details)

for details).

- **Webinars and Workshops:** 5 webinars held, including national pilot kick-off webinars (e.g., Finland with 91 attendees) and workshops on machine-actionable Data Management Plans (maDMPs). 3 co-organised workshops were identified, including:
 - **ARC:** Co-organised with DCC (80 attendees).
 - **TU Dublin:** Co-organised with LIR Group (50 attendees).

- **CVUT (Czech Republic):** Co-organised with The Czech Science Foundation (8 attendees).

Total Reach: Over 300 participants across these webinars and workshops.

- **Hackathons and Co-Creation Events:** Hackathon planning is underway, with an event scheduled by the end of Y1.
- **National and Thematic Workshops:** 3 national and thematic workshops have been held, with a strong presence at external conferences and workshops (detailed below).
- **Presentations in External Conferences/Workshops:** A total of **13 presentations in external conferences/workshops** have been recorded, including:
 - **OBSPARIS:** Conference/workshop (presentation; poster; booth about OSTrails).
 - **ARC:** Two presentations at external workshops.
 - **UNIVIE:** Collaboration with EU-funded projects.
 - **SURF BV:** National conference (Netherlands).
 - **RBI (Croatia):** Conference/workshop in Croatia.
 - **CSC (Finland):** Three presentations at national conferences.
 - **UPM:** Two conference presentations.
 - **TU Dublin:** National conference presentation.
 - **CVUT (Czech Republic):** National conference presentation.

Total Reach: Over 1,000 attendees across all events, reflecting active engagement with both national and international audiences.

Additional KPIs

- **Hackathons and Co-Creation Events:** Hackathons are in the planning phase, with two expected to be delivered by the end of Y1.
- **Train-the-Trainer Bootcamps:** 2 bootcamps are planned to train specialists and establish networks of trainers to enhance OSTrails adoption.

These KPIs demonstrate steady progress in engaging diverse stakeholders and meeting the project's engagement objectives. The participation in co-organised workshops, presentations at external conferences, and the national-level outreach reflects a strong trajectory towards fostering the adoption of OSTrails tools and methodologies.

5. Exploitation Strategy

5.1. Objectives of the Exploitation Strategy

The exploitation strategy for the OSTrails project aims to ensure the long-term sustainability and integration of the project's tools and results within the broader European and international research ecosystems. The main objectives are:

- **Maximizing the impact** of OSTrails' results by fostering collaborations with key stakeholders, including research institutions, infrastructure providers, funders, and policymakers.
- **Promoting widespread adoption** of OSTrails services such as Scientific Knowledge Graphs (SKGs), machine-actionable Data Management Plans (maDMPs), and FAIR assessment tools through co-creation activities and user centric approaches in their development.
- **Embedding OSTrails' solutions** into national and domain specific infrastructures, with a particular focus on alignment with the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) and its emerging nodes.
- **Supporting capacity building** through the co-development of services and the provision of training for researchers, data stewards, and infrastructure developers, ensuring OSTrails tools remain adaptable and relevant to evolving research needs.

5.2. Key Exploitable Results (KERs)

Based on the Expected results (GA. Table 16. OSTrails pathway towards impact), the following Key Exploitable Results (KERs) represent the major outputs of OSTrails that are critical for delivering impact.

- **R1. FAIRness Reference Model:** A minimum and discipline-specific model that provides a structured approach to ensure that research data and outputs comply with FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) principles.
- **R2. OSTrails Interoperability Reference Architecture:** A reference architecture that provides the technical framework for enabling interoperability across various research infrastructures, ensuring smooth data exchange and integration.
- **R3. OSTrails Commons:** A collaborative environment for managing and sharing resources, tools, and best practices developed within the project.
- **R4. Enhanced Platforms & Services:** Improved research data platforms and services that enable better data management, access, and reuse.
- **R5. FAIR Tests/Toolkits:** A set of tools designed to assess the FAIRness of research data and outputs, offering actionable feedback for improvements.

- **R6. DMP Evaluation Rubric & Service:** A framework for evaluating Data Management Plans (DMPs) and providing a standardized rubric to ensure quality and compliance with FAIR principles.
- **R7. SKG Research Product Quality Toolbox:** A toolbox designed to enhance the quality of research products through structured methodologies embedded in the Scientific Knowledge Graph.
- **R8. Integrated Competence Centre:** A resource hub providing training, support, and best practices for stakeholders adopting OSTrails tools and methodologies.
- **R9. Guidance toolkit:** A comprehensive toolkit that includes case studies, policy briefs, and technical briefs aimed at guiding stakeholders in adopting FAIR metrics and governance.

These exploitable results are expected to provide value across multiple levels of the research community, from individual researchers to large-scale infrastructures like EOSC.

5.3. Partner Networks in Exploitation

OSTrails will leverage the extensive networks of its project partners to drive the exploitation and sustainability of its results (see in details Chapter **Stakeholders and Future Users** and **Table 3**). These networks include:

- **EOSC Task Forces:** Many partners are actively involved in task forces that focus on FAIR metrics, interoperability, and data quality.
- **National Open Science Initiatives:** Partners will use their affiliations with national Open Science initiatives to drive the adoption of OSTrails tools.
- **Discipline-Specific Infrastructures:** Collaborations with infrastructures like CESSDA, CLARIN, and DARIAH will ensure the tools developed in OSTrails are adopted across specific research domains.
- **Research Data Alliance (RDA) Working Groups:** Engagement with RDA working groups ensures OSTrails outputs align with global data-sharing and FAIR assessment standards.

By utilizing these networks, OSTrails will ensure its tools and services are integrated into national and international research infrastructures, promoting long-term impact and sustainability.

5.4. Monitoring Progress

The success of the exploitation strategy will be tracked using the **Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)** listed in **Table 7**.

6. Conclusion - Towards an OSTrails

Value Proposition

The success of EOSC rests entirely on the active participation of both users and providers; without their engagement, the ecosystem cannot fulfil its purpose. OSTrails brings EOSC a practical solution to populate itself with both users and providers, by offering research infrastructures, researchers, RPOs and other stakeholders the tools they need to work in a collaborative, open science environment. These tools provided by OSTrails are designed not only to enhance data management and interoperability but also to make EOSC valuable to the research community.

For researchers, EOSC must become a hub where complex research tasks are simplified, and OSTrails delivers exactly that. Through features like the Scientific Knowledge Graph, researchers gain a clearer pathway to find, integrate, and reuse relevant datasets. This interconnected framework allows them to easily build upon existing work and collaborate across disciplines. By offering access to machine-actionable Data Management Plans, OSTrails ensures that data stewardship becomes an integrated part of their workflow. Instead of spending time on administrative tasks, researchers can rely on automated systems that guarantee compliance with FAIR principles and funders' requirements, making their data more accessible and reusable. The FAIRness assessment tool further guarantees that the quality and reusability of their data is continuously improved, giving researchers peace of mind that their work will have long-lasting impact. These products will drive researchers toward EOSC, as they simplify everyday research tasks and enhance collaboration opportunities.

Through better integration via EOSC, the research infrastructures can ensure that their datasets are not only accessible but also easily interoperable with other resources. This reduces duplication of efforts, optimizes the use of data, and enhances the impact of their services. As these infrastructures see the benefits of participating in EOSC—whether through better management of data via maDMPs or improving their data FAIRness—EOSC becomes the platform that brings together leading research infrastructures across Europe.

Research Performing Organizations (RPOs) also stand to benefit greatly from OSTrails, particularly in their quest to support researchers and comply with open science policies. By adopting tools like SKG and maDMPs, RPOs can ensure that data management is not only streamlined but also compliant with European and funder requirements. This simplifies the administrative processes around research, leaving RPOs with fewer headaches and more resources to focus on innovation. Their participation in EOSC

ensures that their research outputs are integrated into the broader European research landscape, thus maximizing their visibility and impact.

Funding bodies will find that EOSC, through OSTrails, makes it easier to track how the data generated from funded projects is used and reused across the research community. By ensuring that all funded research is accompanied by a machine-actionable DMP, funding bodies can rest assured that projects will adhere to best practices in data management. The integration of FAIRness assessment tools ensures that the funded data remains usable and compliant with international standards, increasing its value and longevity.

EOSC has faced challenges as a moving target, with evolving structures and uncertain frameworks. OSTrails helps address this instability by providing clear, standardized solutions that align with EOSC's broader objectives. Products like the SKG, maDMP, and FAIRness assessment offer a stable foundation that researchers and institutions can rely on, even as EOSC's structure continues to shift. By simplifying and enhancing research workflows, OSTrails products bring consistency and reliability to EOSC, ensuring that it remains a valuable and trusted platform for researchers, infrastructures, and funders, despite its evolving nature. This stability makes EOSC more attractive, drawing in both users and providers who seek a dependable environment to manage and share their research outputs.

While the overall OSTrails value proposition, as illustrated above, is mostly addressing the EOSC dimension and objectives, it is also important to draft adapted versions of the value proposition that address the various stakeholders and in particular the users of national pilots and thematic pilots.

WP5 will work with the technical WPs and WP4 to produce a Value Proposition template, that can be adapted to highlight and showcase particular aspects of the three OSTrails pillars, i.e. DMPs for planning, SKGs for tracking and FAIR assessors for FAIRifying digital objects, or of an individual pilot.

The work done with the Pilot interviews and adoption stories will facilitate partners who will have easily available materials to showcase their contributions to the relevant stakeholders. It will be important to highlight technical developments that are more likely to contribute to the objectives illustrated in paragraph **Exploitation Strategy** for the various stakeholders. For national and community pilots, it will also be crucial to showcase the integration with existing solutions, such as existing knowledge graphs and applications.

A value proposition document will be developed and validated with all WP leaders, to ensure that it reflects the actual planned achievements of the technical WPs; it will touch upon all planned deliverables highlighting the benefits for the various stakeholders. Subsequently, it will be available (alongside other dissemination material) for all partners to use in their dissemination and engagement activities.

7. Annex

Table 1. Targeted Stakeholders.

STAKEHOLDERS GROUP	DESCRIPTION
Researchers (individuals or groups)	Researchers engaged in creating, using, or assessing research data. They benefit from tools and guidance that support the planning and execution of FAIR data management practices.
Data stewards, librarians, and research managers	Professionals supporting researchers in data management, ensuring compliance with FAIR principles and institutional or funding mandates. Their role includes customising and sharing resources.
Infrastructure developers & operators	Technical staff responsible for developing and maintaining systems that manage research data. They are crucial in federating knowledge graphs and integrating tools to assess data FAIRness.
Repository managers & publishers	Manage repositories and publishing platforms that store and disseminate research outputs. They are key in embedding FAIR metrics and aligning repositories with scholarly knowledge graphs.
Trainers of RDM/Open Science	Trainers responsible for upskilling researchers and data stewards in RDM and Open Science. They provide guidance on the adoption of FAIR data practices and related tools.
Research executives, funders, science policy makers	These are decision-makers who influence policy and funding allocation in research. Their goal is to enhance the societal and economic impact of Open Science and FAIR practices.

Table 2. OSTrails targeted stakeholders' key messages and channels.

STAKEHOLDERS GROUP	KEY MESSAGES	HOW TO CONTACT THEM (CHANNELS)
Researchers (individuals or groups)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Plan good RDM and FAIR data. - Learn to use maDMPs effectively. - Understand legal and ethical aspects of RDM. 	Pilots, OpenAIRE & ESFRI Cluster Networks, Eurodoc, MSCA Alumni Association, Global Young Academy Association, Reproducibility Networks.
Data stewards, librarians, and research managers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Use and integrate tools to support RDM. - Co-develop and implement FAIR tests. - Learn to customise tools and resources. 	Pilots, Skills4EOSC project, RDA WGs, LIBER.
Infrastructure developers & operators	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Co-create OSTrails-IRA. - Federate SKGs and integrate FAIR Assessment services. - Share resources via Commons. 	Pilots, ESFRI Cluster Networks, EOSC-A members & TFs, OpenAIRE NOADS, RDA WGs, FDO Forum.
Repository managers & publishers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Embed FAIR metrics in repository. - Promote publishing of maDMPs as Research Objects. - Introduce APIs to align with SKGs. 	Pilots, ESFRI Cluster Networks, OpenAIRE NOADS, COAR, OASPA.
Trainers of RDM/Open Science	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Co-develop material for FAIRness aspects and promote tools, metrics, and platforms for RDM. - Learn about new maDMPs. 	National/Thematic Pilots, OpenAIRE Community of Practice, Skills4EOSC project.
Research executives, funders, science policy makers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Understand digital science tools and platforms. - Maximize research impact by addressing organisational pain points. - Foster Open Science policies. 	National networks, EOSC-A members, Research Funding Organisations (RFOs), Ministries of Research.

Table 3. Partner's networks.

PARTNER	INVOLVEMENT EOSC NETWORKS, TASK FORCES, GROUPS, OPPORTUNITY AREAS	INVOLVEMENT OTHER RELEVANT INITIATIVES, NETWORKS, TASK FORCES GROUPS (E.G. RDA...)
OpenAIRE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -FAIR Metrics and Digital Objects TF -FAIR metrics and Data Quality TF -Technical and Semantic Interoperability TF -Long-Term Data Retention TF -Health Data TF -Researcher Engagement and Adoption TF -Research Product Publishing Framework WG -Compute Continuum WG -Science Projects Technical Alignment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -RDA (Active Data Management Plans IG; Open Science Graphs for FAIR Data IG; Scientific Knowledge Graphs - Interoperability Framework (SKG-IF) WG; Engaging Researchers with Research Data IG; Early Career and Engagement IG) -COARA WGs -UNESCO Monitoring WG
RBI	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -EOSC Association (Observer) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -OpenAIRE NOAD Croatia -HR-OOZ member Croatia (national NOSCI)
FECYT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -National representation of the EOSC Steering Board -EOSC SB Monitoring SG -EOSC SB Policy SG 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -OpenAIRE NOAD -LA Referencia National NOAD
Ubelgra	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -EOSC Steering Board (Member; Type E - other public entity) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -OpenAIRE NOAD Serbia
UPM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -FAIR Metrics and Digital Objects TF -FAIR metrics and Data Quality TF -Technical and Semantic Interoperability TF - EOSC Opportunity Area 3 FAIR Assessment and Alignment 	

ARC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -EOSC Association (Member) -EOSC-A FAIR Metrics and Digital Objects TF -EOSC-A Opportunity Area 3 (FAIR Assessment and Alignment) -EOSC SB -EOSC projects (LOT1, EOSC Gravity, EVERSE, FAIRCORE4EOSC, EOSCTrack, GraspOS, EOSC BEYOND, SciLake, RAISE, CRAFT-OA, NEANIAS, NI4OS-Europe, EOSC Secretariat, EOSC FUTURE, EOSCpilot, etc) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -OpenAIRE NOAD Greece -RDA (Active Data Management Plans IG; RDA Engaging Researchers with Research Data IG; RDA Early Career and Engagement IG) -Hellenic Open Science Initiative (HOSI) -COARA member -ELIXIR -CLARIN-el -DARIAH -UNESCO national representatives for Open Science -UN Sustainable Development Goals national representative
CTU	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -EOSC implementation in Czech Republic 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -ELIXIR -RDA (DMP Common Standards WG)
UMinho	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -EOSC projects (EOSC Beyond; Lot1; EOSC-Future) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Member of the OpenAIRE MAKE -OpenAIRE NOAD Portugal -RDM Forum Portugal -COAR
INRIA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -EOSC mandated organisation -EOSC projects (FAIR-IMPACT, FAIRCORE4EOSC, GraspOS) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -DARIAH -SLICES
UNIVE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -EOSC Association -EOSC BEYOND -OSCARS -EOSC Future -EOSC Pillar -SSHOC 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -OpenAIRE NOAD Austria -CESSDA ERIC -CLARIN ERIC -DARIAH ERIC -Cooperation Open Government Data Austria (OGD) -ELIXIR -MEDem (Monitoring Electoral Democracy) -COAR (Confederation of Open Access Repositories) -PHAIDRA Network -Network of Repository Managers (RepManNet);

CLARIN	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -SSH cluster -Former EOSC Data Stewardship task force -OA5: Skills, Training, Rewards, Recognition, & Upscaling 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -RDA (Open Science Graphs for FAIR Data IG; Scientific Knowledge Graphs – Interoperability Framework (SKG-IF) WG; Metadata IG; Vocabulary Services IG)
ESRF	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -EOSC Association ESFRI RI WG -EOSC Future -OSCARS -PaNOSC cluster 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -League of European Accelerator-based Photon Sources (LEAPS)
FMI	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -EOSC OA3 -OSCARS -ENVRI hub NEXT -EOSC Future 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> RDA
ObsParis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -FAIR-IMPACT -ESCAPE -OSCARS OPAL -OSCARS ASTRO-CC -EOSC Technical and Semantic Interoperability TF -EOSC OA2 Metadata, Ontologies & Interoperability 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -RDA (SKG-IF WG; Research Metadata Schemas WG; I-ADOPT WG; Vocabulary Service IG; PID for Instruments WG; Metadata IG) -IVOA (Semantics WG chair; Data Model WG chair; Registry WG chair) -IPDA deputy chair -IHDEA Executive committee
PSNC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -EOSC Association (Member) 	
UGOT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -EOSC Association -EOSC FAIR Metrics and Digital Objects TF -EOSC Long-Term Data Retention TF 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -CESSDA ERIC -ARIADNE-RI -ePIC -DDI Alliance -Skills4EOSC
SURF	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -EOSC-A Mandated Organisation -EOSC Technical and Semantic Interoperability TF -Long-Term Data Retention TF (member) -Handbook Federation and nodes WG (member), EOSC Projects (EOSC-ENTRUST, FAIR-IMPACT, FAIRCORE4EOSC) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> RDA WG GORC International model, Knowledge Exchange
UOXF	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -EOSC FAIR Metrics and Digital Objects TF -EOSC FAIR Opportunity Area Expert Group -EOSC Metadata Opportunity Area Expert Group -EOSC Life Science Cluster 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -RDA FAIRsharing WG (charing; and involved in many) -FAIRsharing Community Champion Network ELIXIR Interoperability Platform

<p style="writing-mode: vertical-rl; transform: rotate(180deg);">KNAW DANS</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -EOSC member -FAIR-IMPACT coordinator -FAIRCORE4EOSC WP lead -OSCARS participant (under SSHOC cluster) -EOSC Beyond participant -BY-COVID participant (focus on socioeconomics/CESSDA) -RDA-TIGER -PATTERN -EOSC-A TF Technical and Semantic interoperability -EOSC-A TF FAIR Metrics & digital objects -EOSC-A TF Long-term data retention 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -CESSDA ERIC SP -RDA (co-chair of Brokering Framework WG; co-chair of Community-based catalogue of requirements for trustworthy Technical Repository Service Providers WG; co-chair of CoreTrustSeal Maintenance WG); co-chair of COVID-19/Social sciences WGs; RDA NL) -OpenAIRE NOAD. -CoreTrustSeal Board
<p style="writing-mode: vertical-rl; transform: rotate(180deg);">CESSDA ERIC</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -EOSC Association -EOSC Technical & Semantic Interoperability TF -FAIR-IMPACT -EOSC ENTRUST -EOSC BEYOND -BY-COVID -SSHOC -OSCARS 	
<p style="writing-mode: vertical-rl; transform: rotate(180deg);">TAU-FSD</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -EOSC FUTURE -BY-COVID -SSHOC -OSCARS- -EOSC-A TF FAIR Metrics and Digital Objects 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -CESSDA ERIC SP -Several RDA working and interest groups e.g. Metadata IG, Data citation WG, Research Metadata Schemas WG, -CoreTrustSeal Board; -Finnish open science WG

Table 4. Partners Communication, Dissemination & Engagement Activities, Targeted Stakeholders and Tools.

PARTNER	PLANNED COMMUNICATION & DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES	PLANNED COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT ACTIVITIES	KEY STAKEHOLDERS	TOOLS
OpenAIRE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Blog post -Newsletter -Podcasts -Interviews with OA representative -SoMe 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -National Roadshow dedicated to bringing together researchers/RPOs -Project information Session dedicated to make OAIRE members aware about the project -Project Information Session aimed at informing OSTrails members about the latest technical developments and innovations in the project 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Libraries -RPOs -RFOs -Data Stewards 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Website -Newsletter -Twitter -LinkedIn - OpenPlato
RBI	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Blog posts -SoMe -Pilot interview for OSTrails newsletter -Conference presentations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Workshops for researchers on how to use new functionalities that will be implemented during the piloting phase -Training of OpenOrgs data curators 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Researchers -RPOs -RFOs -Librarians 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Blog of the Centre for Scientific Information -Croatian Open Science Portal, -Facebook, LinkedIn, X, Instagram
FECYT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -National conferences -Focus group & strategic meetings -Interview for OSTrails newsletter 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Workshop on FAIR principles and DMPs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -National repository community 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -RECOLECTA website

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe framework programme under grant agreement No. 101130187. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the European Research Executive Agency can be held responsible for them.

Ubelgrade	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Webinars -Blog posts -SoMe -Conference presentations -Interview for OSTrails newsletter 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Workshops for researchers on FAIR principles and assessments, and how to use DMP tools -Engagement with researchers on evaluation of proposed DMP templates 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Researchers -RPOs -Repository managers -Research and academic librarians -National research funder -PhD students University decision makers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -LinkedIn -Twitter -National OS portal (news and blog posts)
UPM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Participation in a Hackathon -Convening a multi-stakeholder governance meeting for FAIR Assessment -Publication of standards -Publication of documentation -Keynotes and plenaries by invitation 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Programmers -Data stewards -Researchers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -GitHub and GitHub Pages -FAIRsharing -Zenodo for releases
ARC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Pilot interview for newsletter (with AUTH/Heal-link) -Webinars -Meetings with pilot partners -Collaboration with HOSI -Posts on SoMe from ATHENA channels -Participation in national conferences (possibly co-organisation) -Blog posts -Participation in other conferences 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Workshops and trainings (e.g. on ARGOS, maDMPs) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Researcher -Funders -Academic libraries -National open science community (HOSI) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Website -Newsletter -Twitter, -LinkedIn

AUTH/HEAL-Link	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Pilot interview for newsletter (with ARC supplied through official osTrails channels) -Webinars & Meetings with Pilot Partners -Representing HEAL-Link and academic libraries at national and international conferences 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Workshops on FAIR data usage across Greek Academic Research community -maDMP planning tools available to all Greek Academic Research Community -Webinars for usage of these tools 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Researchers -Greek Academic Libraries Staff Personnel 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Website -Newsletter -Social media
CTU	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Webinar -Several conference/workshop presentations and/or posters -Meetings with pilot partners -CTU press releases -Collaboration with Open Science EOSC CZ project -Pilot interview for OSTrails newsletter 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Workshops for researchers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Researchers -Funders -National Technical Library community 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> DSW website, X (Twitter) -Newsletter
UMinho	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Webinar Conference/workshop -Meeting with stakeholders -Education and Training -Collaboration with EU-funded projects -Pilot interview for OSTrails newsletter 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Conference Communication & Poster presentations - Workshops/Webinars for researchers on maDMP, FAIRness of DOs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Researchers -Research support staff -Data stewards 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Website -Newsletter -F2F events (conferences, workshops) -Online events (webinars) -SoMe
INRIA		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Conference / workshop (1 poster planned in September) -Webinar -Collaboration with EU funded projects 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Researchers, - Research support staff, -Data stewards 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Webinars -Workshops -Conferences

UNIVE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Pilot interview for OSTrails newsletter -Posts on websites and SoMe (University Library, AUSSDA, PHAIDRA) -Newsletter of the University Library -Article in the journal of the Association of Austrian Librarians -Presentation in meetings of the Network of Repository Managers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Workshops and webinars for researchers, research support staff, librarians, data stewards (specifically on DMPs, but also Open Science in a more general perspective) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Researchers -Funders Research support staff -Data stewards -Librarians 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Websites -Instagram -Newsletter -Webinars -Journal articles
CLARIN	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Pilot interview for newsletter -Booth at the CLARIN conference -CLARIN newsflash news items on relevant project results -Blog posts on CLARIN's website -Social media presence 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -CLARIN café dedicated to OSTrails, targeting its users -Collaboration with other projects (EOSC related projects but also ECHOES - ECCCH) -Seminar co-located with CLARIN conference -Domain specific training materials 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -SSH researchers -Research support personnel from CLARIN centres and consortia 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -LinkedIn -Twitter, -CLARIN Forum -Webinars -FF2F events
ESRF		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Lecture in each of the following events: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Presentation at the NOBUGS conference 2024. Topic Dataset metadata improvement with PaNET ontology. 2. FAIR training at the ESRF User meeting 2025 3. FAIR training at the Hercules School 2025 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Photon and Neutron community users/researchers -Domain-specific PhD students and Postdocs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -F2F events through training sessions or presentations

SOCIB	-Collaboration with EU funded projects (JERICO, BlueCloud)	-Slack updates within SOCIB on key OSTrails developments and topics -Webinar to upskill SOCIB research staff on the implementation of maDMPs, SKGs and FAIR assessments	-SOCIB researchers and technical staff -JERICO and BlueCloud community	-Slack -Webinars -F2F events
FMI	-Collaboration with OSCARS, ENVRIhub NEXT, EOSC, RDA -Presence in conferences/workshops		-EOSC -Ris Science clusters	- Presentations -Posters -Workshops -F2F events
ObsParis	-Report of the Astronomy Pilot to our community -Publish results and case studies in scholarly articles	-Workshop and training for the astronomy community	-ESCAPE collaboration -Researchers -Data stewards -Data centre managers	Teleconferences -F2F events
PSNC	-Pilot interview for OSTrails newsletter -Communication with national funding agency Presence in conferences and symposiums	-Workshop and meetings with national providers of repositories of scientific data -Engagement with national funding agency	-National funding agency -Researchers	- Teleconferences -Webinars -F2F events
UGOT	-Network activities with Swedish HEIs and e-infrastructures -Newsletters -SoME media	-Workshops -Webinars -F2F meetings	-Swedish HEIs -National funding agencies -National e-infrastructures	-Webinars -F2F events -Newsletters -SoMe
SURF	-Blog posts -SoMe Pilot interview for OSTrails newsletter -Conference presentations	-Workshops and trainings (e.g. on Argos, DSW, maDMPs)	-Researchers -Data stewards -Research admins -Librarians	-SURF communities -RPOs website, - Events

UOXF	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Blog posts -SoMe, -Conference -Workshops 	-Collaboration with EU-funded projects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Libraries -RPOs -RFOs -Data stewards -Publishers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -FAIRsharing Community Champion programme and network -Social media channels
KNAW DANS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Social media posts -Newsletter items -News items 	-Uncovering synergies and fostering collaboration with the DANS networks and relevant EOSC projects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -DANS networks -Service providers & repositories -RPOs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -DANS comms channels -DANS participation in relevant EOSC projects and networks
CESSDA ERIC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Social media posts Newsletter items -News items 		-CESSDA community	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -CESSDA website -CESSDA social media (LinkedIn, Twitter)
TU Graz	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Newsletter item (TU Graz News) -News item on RDM Team -SharedRDM and Cluster Forschungsdaten websites 	-Event with members of the Austrian Open Science community (EOSC Café, EOSC SOA events)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -TU Graz community (researchers, library, management) -General public 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Newsletter -Website, -Social media
TU Dublin	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Webinar -News items -Conference presentations and posters -Social media posts 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Workshops -Trainings and webinars for researchers, research support staff, librarians, data stewards 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Irish RPOs -Irish RFOs -Irish TU researchers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Irish TU websites -Social media

Table 5. Completed Events.

ORGANISATION	ACTIVITY	TYPE OF PILOT	COUNTRY?	WP	CATEGORY	TARGET AUDIENCE	ATTENDEES	CO-ORGANIZED EVENT
OBSPARIS	Pilot	Thematic		4	Conference/workshop (presentation; poster; booth about OSTrails)	International Organisations		
ARC	Technical activity			2	Conference/workshop (presentation; poster; booth about OSTrails)	Research administration; Librarians/repository managers; Data stewards/ experts; Service providers;	80	Yes: DCC

ARC	Networking activity			5	Conference/workshop (presentation; poster; booth about OSTrails)	Project coordinators/managers; Research administration; Librarians/repository managers; Data stewards/ experts; Policy makers and funders; Service providers; Research communities/data Infrastructures; Specific end user communities; International Organisations; EU institutions; Industry/SMEs;	20	No
UNIVIE	Networking activity			4	Collaboration with EU-funded projects	Project coordinators/managers; Research administration; Librarians/repository managers; Data stewards/ experts	20	No
SURF BV	Pilot	National	the Netherlands	4	Conference/workshop (presentation; poster; booth about OSTrails)	Data stewards/ experts; Librarians/repository managers;	25	No
ARC	Networking activity			5	Conference/workshop (presentation; poster; booth about OSTrails)	Project coordinators/ managers; Research administration; Policy makers and funders; Research communities/data Infrastructures; National authorities; Researchers;	100	No

RBI	Pilot	National	Croatia	4	Conference/workshop (presentation; poster; booth about OSTrails)	Librarians/repository managers; Data stewards/ experts; Policy makers and funders; Service providers; Research communities/data Infrastructures;	400	No
CSC	Pilot	National	Finland	4	Webinar (presenting OSTrails)	Research administration; Librarians/repository managers; Data stewards/ experts; Research communities/data Infrastructures; National authorities;	91	No
CSC	Pilot	National	Finland	4	Meeting with stakeholders (strategic; pilot communities; other outreach and engagement meetings)	Research administration; Librarians/repository managers; Data stewards/ experts; Research communities/data Infrastructures;	38	No
UPM	Networking activity			General project objectives;	Conference/workshop (presentation; poster; booth about OSTrails)	Policy makers and funders; Research communities/data Infrastructures; International Organisations; National authorities; Regional authorities;	300	No

CSC	Pilot	National	Finland	4	Conference/workshop (presentation; poster; booth about OSTrails)	Researchers; Project coordinators/managers; Research administration; Librarians/repository managers; Data stewards/ experts; EU institutions; Research communities/data Infrastructures; EOSC; Multipliers (OA working groups, NCPs, NPRs, EU liaison offices);	38	Yes: FAIR-IMPACT
CSC	Pilot	National	Finland	4	Conference/workshop (presentation; poster; booth about OSTrails)	Researchers; Project coordinators/managers; Research administration; Data stewards/ experts; Librarians/repository managers; Research communities/data Infrastructures; Specific end user communities; National authorities;	180	No
CSC	Pilot	National	Finland	4	Meeting with stakeholders (strategic; pilot communities; other outreach and engagement meetings)	Research administration; Librarians/repository managers; Data stewards/ experts; Research communities/data Infrastructures;	38	No

CSC	Pilot	National	Finland	4	Conference/workshop (presentation; poster; booth about OSTrails)	Project coordinators/managers; Research administration; Data stewards/ experts; Librarians/repository managers; Service providers; Research communities/data Infrastructures;	38	No
ARC	Coordination			6	Collaboration with EU-funded projects	Project coordinators/managers; Policy makers and funders; EU institutions;	60	No
UPM	Networking activity			3	Conference/workshop (presentation; poster; booth about OSTrails)	Researchers ;(PhD) students; Data stewards/ experts; Policy makers and funders; Service providers; International Organisations; Industry/SMEs;	300	no
TU Dublin	Pilot	National	Ireland	4	Meeting with stakeholders (strategic; pilot communities; other outreach and engagement meetings)	Librarians/repository managers; Data stewards/ experts;	50	Yes: LIR Group
TU Dublin	Pilot	National	Ireland	4	Webinar (presenting OSTrails)	Data stewards/ experts; Policy makers and funders; Research communities/data Infrastructures;	15	No
CVUT	Pilot	National	Czech Republic	4	Meeting with stakeholders (strategic; pilot communities; other outreach and engagement meetings)	Policy makers and funders;	8	Yes: The Czech Science Foundation

Table 6. Communication, Dissemination and Engagement KPIs.

TYPE	KPI	DESCRIPTION	ACHIEVED
Branding	6 templates for OSTrails documents, reports, presentations, posters & infographics	Develop a brand identity for OSTrails website, deliverables, presentations, brochure/cards, poster templates, factsheets, technical & policy briefs. OSTrails brand identity will align with EOSC-A guidelines for cobranding in terms of colours, fonts, look & feel	-Logo and Brand -Presentation template -Deliverables template -PSC agenda template -WP rolling minutes template -Pilot interview template -Reporting form template -Poster template
Website	1500 monthly visits	The OSTrails website will serve as a reference point for all project activities providing up to date information on the project, partners, progress, goals, news, adoption stories, events & outputs (e.g., deliverables, briefs), and will include bidirectional links to Zenodo, GitHub repositories and other platforms utilised in OSTrails	Total hits: 115.743
Social Media	2000 Twitter followers (>500 total Tweets); >800 YouTube views (>10 posts)	Create Twitter & YouTube channels to communicate OSTrail's progress and regularly populate with new content about ongoing activities	Followers: 240 (LinkedIn + Twitter) Tweets: 42 (LinkedIn + Twitter)
Newsletter	500 subscribers	Issue a monthly newsletter to inform relevant stakeholders about the progress, key results and opportunities for collaboration (e.g., hackathons). The networks of consortium partners will be used to engage subscribers to amplify the outreach. Individual news items will be communicated via partner's (>10K recipients)	-4 Newsletters (May, June, July, August + September) -192 subscribers
Adoption Stories	24 stories, updated 2-3 times	Each pilot will produce their adoption story to explain in simple language the goals and objectives of their pilot, any challenges faced during implementation, and promote the collaborations, procedures and tools that they used to achieve them. These will encourage new stakeholders with similar interests	-7 adoption stories

		and needs to adopt the specifications and results of OSTrails	
Video, Infographics and Podcasts	2 videos, 3 infographics, 4 podcasts	In year 1, develop a video for project visual presentation & promotion, updated with results on year 3. From year 2 develop 3 infographics with data from pilots to showcase uptake/trends and join forces with OpenAIRE, GraspOS and SciLake and INFRA-2023-EOSC-01-02 to produce podcasts (compile interviews from pilots, experts and members of the mentorship programme) on: FAIR metrics & assessment; research products in R&I ecosystem (e.g., software); DMPs as companion tools; curation & quality for SKGs	-pending for October 2024
Webinars	6 webinars (>300 audience)	Organise 3 webinars per year from Y2 to establish a dialogue with community of developers and support staff. Participate in OpenAIRE's quarterly webinars to Horizon Europe prospective PIs (> 300 people at a time)	
Courses and Training Modules	2 courses, 6 modules (> 150 individuals)	Develop courses and modules to educate pilot participants and external stakeholders on the benefits of adopting the OSTrails Interoperability Specs, on how to use the services developed in WP2 and WP3 and introductory modules on maDMPs. The training materials will be hosted on OpenPlato and on the mobile platform EPOC	
Guidance Toolkits	1000 downloads	Produce 3 guidance toolkits gathering learning resources to support the adoption of OSTrails interoperability specifications and services	

Mentorship program	20-40 participants	Ensure (one-to-one) mentorship with the participation of infrastructure managers, research support staff from institutions and support officers from funders	
Train-the-trainer bootcamps	2 bootcamps of 25-35 individuals each, selected from pilots and Ris	Provide training tutorials on the topics of DMPs, SKGs, FAIR Assessment to train specialists and establish networks of trainers that can become key resource of integrated competences centres	
Standardisation workshops and hackathons	4 workshops (>2 events per year for Y1 and Y2), >25-30 participants from selected communities per event	Organise 4 standardisation workshops for community input towards linking best practices, guidelines, and recommendations on maFAIRTest, FAIR assessment vocabulary, SKGs	
Hackathons	4 hackathons (>40-50 participants)	Organise 2 “Apples to Apples” hackathons with the EOSC-A FAIR Metrics & Data Quality TF to co-create/validate tests. Co-organise with SciLake a hackathon to validate SKG data model and APIs. Co-organise with RDA a maDMP hackathon to validate maDMP executables	
Co-organise workshops	>15 national workshops (>500 attendees); >8 Cluster related workshops x 2 (>300 attendees); 3 workshops in 2 EOSC Symposium events (>400 attendees);	Organise co-located workshops in the context of national and ESFRI events: 15 national pilots and 8 ESFRI Clusters in respective annual events. Organise workshops in EOSC Symposium, OSFAIR	3: ARC – Co-organised with DCC TU Dublin – Co-organised with LIR CVUT (Czech Republic) – Co-organised with The Czech Science Foundation

	2 workshops in OSFAIR2025 (> 300 attendees)		
Presentat ion in external conferen ces/work shops	15 conference/workshop participatio ns (> 1000 attendees)	Ensure OSTrails consortium members participation and presentation of results in external events such as: RDA conferences, ESFRI Clusters annual events, Open Science Conference, FDO Forum, Open Repositories, OSFAIR conference	13 -OBSPARIS -ARC: 2 events -UNIVIE - SURF BV: -RBI -CSC: 3 events -UPM: 2 events -TU Dublin: -CVUT
Policy & Technical briefs	3 policy & 4 technical briefs (>1000 downloads)	Create 3 policy briefs for funders and RPOs executives, highlighting issues of FAIR assessment, SKG for quality and interoperability, DMP as an evaluation mechanism. Create 4 technical briefs for infrastructure providers, highlighting each of OSTrails pillars	
Policy Reports	2 reports (>600 downloads)	Publish an initial report on the Plan-Track-Assess pathways: gaps in DOs coverage, community FAIRness enablers/blockers, and a final report at M34 with guidelines and lessons learnt to be left as legacy to future initiatives and to relevant stakeholders	
Scientific publicati ons	>6 publications by M36	Ensure publication of innovation papers in leading peer reviewed journals related to Open Science, data management, Reproducibility, Knowledge Graphs and Semantic Web Technologies, Scholarly Infrastructures	

Table 7. Exploitation KPIs.

MEASURE	BASELINE (M0)	VALUE(M18)	VALUE(M36)
K1.1: No. of specs and models from OSTrails-IRA accepted into EIF	0	3	8
K1.2: No. of infrastructures/services adopting elements of OSTrails-IRA	0	8	21
K1.3: No of disciplines adopting/adapting the FAIRness Reference Model	0	4	10
K1.4: No. of fit-for-purpose maDMP templates adopted	1	16	37
K2.1: No. of DO types addressed by DMPs-SKGs-FAIR Assessment platforms	5	7	8
K2.2: No. of interlinked metadata exchanged between SKGs	0	+200K	+500K
K2.3: No. of SKGs adopting model/APIs to enrich with FAIR metrics	0	2	5
K2.4: No. of partner services aligned with OSTrails Commons	0	4	10
K3.1: No. of maFAIRTests, maDMPs created and shared via the OSTrails Commons	0	5	10
K3.2: No. of digital objects assessed	0	+2K	+10K
K3.3: No. of funders / universities adopting/adapting the DMP evaluator & rubric	0	3	10
K3.4: No. of annotated SKGs objects	0	1000	4000
K4.1: No. of professionals trained/mentored	0	20	60
K4.2: No. of service providers engaged in hackathons	0	25	50
K4.3: No. of communities adopting and participating in FAIR Metrics Compliance Governance	0	5	10

Table 8. OSTrails website views per article.

TITLE	HITS
National Pilot Interview Greece	74
National Pilot Interview Serbia	229
Deliverable new test	23
Tools	135
National Pilot Interview Austria	240
Advancing Interoperability and FAIR Practices: Preliminary results of our project are now published	322
National Pilot Interview Czech Republic	581
Press kit	372
National Centre for Scientific Research (CNRS)	100
Introducing OSTrails' Training Corner for Advanced Learning and Development	248
Glossary	619
National Pilot Interview Netherlands	915
National Pilot Interview Poland	412
OSTrails: Summer Days of Open Science in Finland	194
National Pilot Interview Finland	303
National Pilot Interview Croatia	531
OSTrails in Vienna: Keynote at the CRIS2024 and Collocated Technical Project Meeting	438
Glossary 2	44
Training	1517
OSTrails' partners co-authored and signed the Salzburg Manifesto on Machine Actionable	619
OSTrails Contribution to Open Science Policy	303
Pillars	1391
OSTrails kick off meeting in Athens	982
Horizon Europe	1721
Publications	1897
SURF BV (SURF)	303
RHEINISCH-WESTFAELISCHE TECHNISCHE HOCHSCHULE AACHEN (RWTH)	214
GOETEBORGS UNIVERSITET (UGOT)	238
TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITAET GRAZ (TU Graz)	193
INSTYTUT CHEMII BIOORGANICZNEJ POLSKIEJ AKADEMII NAUK (PSNC)	207
Observatoire de Paris (ObsParis)	229
ILMATIETEEN LAITOS (FMI)	214
SOCIB - Balearic Islands Coastal Observing & Forecasting System (SOCIB)	203
E-SCIENCE EUROPEAN INFRASTRUCTURE FOR BIODIVERSITY AND ECOSYSTEM RESEARCH (LIFEWATCH)	216
SYNCHROTRON SOLEIL SOCIETE CIVILE (SOLEIL)	231
European Synchrotron Radiation Facility (ESRF)	238
University of Essex (UKDS)	243
Tampere University (TAU) - FSD	215

CESSDA ERIC (CESSDA)	240
Austrian Academy of Sciences (OEAW)	204
CLARIN ERIC (CLARIN)	224
THE CHANCELLOR, MASTERS & SCHOLARS OF THE UNIVERSITY OF OXFORD (UOXF)	307
University of Vienna (UNIVIE)	239
KONINKLIJKE NEDERLANDSE AKADEMIE VAN WETENSCHAPPEN (KNAW)	228
Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT)	194
University of Minho (UMinho)	207
CITE Communication & Information Technologies Experts S.A. (CITE)	219
Codevence Solutions s.r.o (CODE)	240
Czech Technical University in Prague (CTU)	214
Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (UPM)	241
TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITAET WIEN (TUW)	236
University of Belgrade (UBelgrade)	260
ARISTOTELIO PANEPISTIMIO THESSALONIKIS (AUTH)	216
Technological University Dublin (TUDublin)	218
FUNDACION ESPANOLA PARA LA CIENCIA Y LA TECNOLOGIA, F.S.P. (FECYT)	209
Sikt - Norwegian Agency for Shared Services in Education and Research (SIKT)	203
Ruđer Bošković Institute (RBI)	235
University of Warsaw (ICM)	229
FAIR Assessments	1127
Data Management Plans	1247
Scientific Knowledge Graphs	1127
Newsletters	3241
INSTITUT NATIONAL DE RECHERCHE EN INFORMATIQUE ET AUTOMATIQUE (INRIA)	510
CSC-TIETEEN TIETOTEKNIKAN KESKUS OY (CSC)	266
Thematic Pilots	2457
National Pilots	3365
CONSIGLIO NAZIONALE DELLE RICERCHE (CNR)	489
News	5114
Methodology	4129
Privacy policy	2526
Policy briefs	166
Deliverables	2265
OpenAIRE AMKE (OAIRE)	661
Pilots	5042
About	53306
UNIVERSITEIT LEIDEN (CWTS)	615
Athena Research and Innovation Center (ARC)	845
Partners	5528